

Artifact - Log Parsing Evaluation in the Era of Modern Software Systems

(1) Artifact Description

This artifact contains information on how to reproduce the experiments of "[Log Parsing Evaluation in the Era of Modern Software Systems](#)", accepted at ISSRE'23.

We provide instructions on how to reproduce the obtained results for each section of the paper. To simplify reproducibility, all experiments are packaged using Docker. We include all necessary software and data used in the paper, enabling either to evaluate log parsing in various scenarios, showcasing the functionality of the tool presented in the paper ([logchimera](#)), or reproducing the paper's figures and tables.

We organize this document with instructions on reproducing each section of the paper that contains experiments, as following:

```
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├─ (1) Artifact Description
├─ (2) Environment Setup
├─ (3) Getting started
├─ (4) Reproducibility Instructions
│   ├─ (4.1) Log parsing scrutinized # Table II, Table III (Section III)
│   ├─ (4.2) Heterogeneity analysis # Figure 4, Table IV (Section III)
│   ├─ (4.3) Proxy metrics weighing # Table V (Section IV)
│   ├─ (4.4) Mixing # Table VI (Section IV)
│   ├─ (4.5) Mixing and fuzzing # Table VII (Section IV)
└─ (4.6) Unlabeled comparison # Table VIII (Section IV)
```

Should you encounter any issues, additional support and examples on reproducing the experiments can be found [here](#).

(2) Environment Setup

As the artifact is packaged using Docker, the only prerequisites for the evaluation are essentially a properly installed and running Docker daemon. Furthermore, having

access to a command line environment is considered to be a prerequisite. In our case, log parsing experiments were run on an AMD server, with Docker version 20.10.5 installed.

Specifically, the experiments were run on the following machines:

- a dual socket AMD Epyc2 machine with 64 cores in total, with a dual Nvidia RTX 2080Ti graphics card setup.
- an Apple M1 Pro machine with 10 cores in total.

In case of experiments that require access to more special resources, such as CUDA enabled GPUs, specific instructions are provided; in such cases, experiments have to be run directly from the sources.

(3) Getting Started

As mentioned in the environment setup, the only prerequisites for the evaluation are essentially a properly installed and running Docker daemon. Instructions on how to install and run Docker can be found [here](#).

To get you started, we showcase the workflow of reproducing an experiment: regardless of the section to be reproduced, other experiments follow a similar setup and workflow, and we consider this example representative. Subsequently, we showcase how to reproduce one cell from Table II and Table III of the [paper](#). After the Docker image is pulled, this experiment should take less than 5 minutes.

Expectation: after following all the steps below, you should expect to have reproduced the first cell of Table II and III, i.e., the measurement for the **AEL** log parsing method tested on the **Apache** dataset, which should output a **0.694** log template accuracy and a **10.426** edit-distance. We consider this example to be representative, as obtaining the results for all the other measurements in the tables follows a similar workflow.

TABLE II
LOG TEMPLATE ACCURACY RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.000	0.688	0.000	0.000	0.694	0.000	0.270	0.560	0.000	0.424	0.694
BGL	0.341	0.341	0.292	0.082	0.230	0.057	0.067	0.220	0.081	0.324	0.853	0.064	0.207	0.196
HDFS	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.000	0.000
HealthApp	0.164	0.238	0.158	0.136	0.149	0.133	0.138	0.220	0.126	0.166	0.341	0.041	0.322	0.152
HPC	0.644	0.620	0.638	0.632	0.609	0.360	0.632	0.632	0.509	0.632	0.827	0.226	0.661	0.530
Mac	0.172	0.224	0.041	0.132	0.101	0.172	0.162	0.228	0.118	0.042	0.274	0.163	0.148	0.032
OpenStack	0.018	0.018	0.000	0.018	0.008	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000	0.359	0.018	0.119	0.000
Spark	0.194	0.194	0.192	0.004	0.190	0.001	0.006	0.038	0.000	0.208	0.204	0.004	0.543	0.192
Windows	0.154	0.159	0.001	0.154	0.142	0.148	0.153	0.156	0.150	0.006	0.387	0.151	0.140	0.004
Combined Dataset	0.267	0.258	0.214	0.140	0.180	0.140	0.128	0.258	0.092	0.180	0.323	0.067	0.280	0.186
Industry Dataset	0.054	0.056	0.041	0.001	0.022	0.001	0.002	0.054	0.000	0.048	0.050	0.002	0.034	0.041

TABLE III
EDIT-DISTANCE RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	10.426	10.426	10.442	13.760	10.576	14.872	16.274	10.426	14.456	10.179	4.679	12.648	11.234	10.442
BGL	5.014	4.930	6.882	8.373	12.524	12.582	12.955	18.598	11.921	10.969	2.981	8.630	9.841	7.900
HDFS	8.820	8.820	16.208	10.762	30.819	17.940	28.340	16.524	18.989	19.843	2.867	10.114	13.641	9.274
HealthApp	19.093	18.502	11.882	16.540	20.277	28.422	16.844	19.598	17.088	21.859	11.595	24.430	13.840	8.540
HPC	1.405	2.015	2.323	2.906	3.182	7.649	3.580	3.218	4.419	4.845	1.275	7.854	2.625	5.129
Mac	19.534	19.882	20.928	19.984	41.804	26.260	21.328	17.048	28.043	28.273	21.417	19.810	34.560	22.593
OpenStack	17.142	28.386	23.330	18.535	28.138	29.173	31.486	23.980	21.881	67.894	5.605	18.582	20.986	27.984
Spark	3.861	3.532	5.246	10.945	9.178	18.116	17.082	16.004	12.968	14.146	2.921	7.910	6.028	6.129
Windows	11.975	6.172	15.758	20.662	10.238	11.834	6.967	6.919	7.667	11.943	6.067	5.624	7.006	4.406
Combined Dataset	13.612	17.302	14.094	18.559	24.144	27.633	21.306	15.858	24.756	19.021	8.721	21.791	22.274	17.454
Industry Dataset	21.959	27.201	24.122	32.280	41.960	68.551	47.006	23.506	37.911	49.145	23.239	31.908	46.690	24.664

Consequently, to get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (Step 1 through 5):

Step 1: Pull the docker image

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py2
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py2 bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python2
```

Step 4: Setup environment

```
$ sh setup_python2.sh
```

Step 5: Run experiment (runs method 10 times)

```
$ sh run_experiment_python2.sh -m AEL -d Apache
# (about 3m)
# (Expect a result of 0.694 log template accuracy and 10.426 edit-distance)
```

`-m` specifies the log parsing method to be used and `-d` the dataset.

To reproduce other results, for example, `Drain` on the `BGL` dataset (second cell on the second line of Table II and III), simply replace the method and dataset to be used, namely:

```
sh run_experiment_python2.sh -m Drain -d BGL
# (about 5m)
# (Expect a result of 0.341 log template accuracy and 4.930 edit-distance)
```

All other experiments in the artifact follow a similar workflow.

(4) Reproducibility Instructions

In this section we describe how to reproduce the paper's results in detail.

We display below the structure of this section: each section refers to particular Tables or Figures to be reproduced. Should you encounter any issues, additional support and examples on reproducing the experiments can be found [here](#).

```
├─ (4) Reproducibility Instructions
│  └─ (4.1) Log parsing scrutinized # Table II, Table III (Section III)
│  └─ (4.2) Heterogeneity analysis # Figure 4, Table IV (Section III)
│  └─ (4.3) Proxy metrics weighing # Table V (Section IV)
│  └─ (4.4) Mixing # Table VI (Section IV)
│  └─ (4.5) Mixing and fuzzing # Table VII (Section IV)
└─ └─ (4.6) Unlabeled comparison # Table VIII (Section IV)
```

(4.1) Log parsing scrutinized (Table II, Table III)

The following methods can be tested, in their respective environment.

We recommend following the methods in sequential order, from 1 to 14.

No.	Method	Python 2	Python 3
1	AEL	X	-
2	Drain	X	-
3	IPLoM	X	-
4	LenMa	X	-
5	LFA	X	-
6	LKE	X	-
7	LogCluster	X	-
8	LogMine	X	-
9	LogSig	X	-
10	SHISO	X	-
11	SLCT	X	-
12	Spell	X	-
13	MoLFI	-	X
14	NuLog	-	X

No.	Dataset
1	Apache
2	BGL
3	HDFS
4	HealthApp
5	HPC
6	Mac
7	OpenStack
8	Spark
9	Windows
10	Combined_Dataset

Method 1-12 (Python 2 log parsing methods)

Expectation: after going through all the steps below (1 through 5), you should expect to have reproduced the highlighted sections in the figure below (Table II and III). We start by showcasing how to reproduce the measurement for **AEL** on the **Apache** dataset, which should output a **0.694** log template accuracy and a **10.426** edit-distance. We consider this example to be representative, as obtaining the results for all the other measurements follows a similar workflow.

TABLE II
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Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.000	0.688	0.000	0.000	0.694	0.000	0.270	0.560	0.000	0.424	0.694
BGL	0.341	0.341	0.292	0.082	0.230	0.057	0.067	0.220	0.081	0.324	0.853	0.064	0.207	0.196
HDFS	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.000	0.000
HealthApp	0.164	0.238	0.158	0.136	0.149	0.133	0.138	0.220	0.126	0.166	0.341	0.041	0.322	0.152
HPC	0.644	0.620	0.638	0.632	0.609	0.360	0.632	0.632	0.509	0.632	0.827	0.226	0.661	0.530
Mac	0.172	0.224	0.041	0.132	0.101	0.172	0.162	0.228	0.118	0.042	0.274	0.163	0.148	0.032
OpenStack	0.018	0.018	0.000	0.018	0.008	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000	0.359	0.018	0.119	0.000
Spark	0.194	0.194	0.192	0.004	0.190	0.001	0.006	0.038	0.000	0.208	0.204	0.004	0.543	0.192
Windows	0.154	0.159	0.001	0.154	0.142	0.148	0.153	0.156	0.150	0.006	0.387	0.151	0.140	0.004
Combined Dataset	0.267	0.258	0.214	0.140	0.180	0.140	0.128	0.258	0.092	0.180	0.323	0.067	0.280	0.186
Industry Dataset	0.054	0.056	0.041	0.001	0.022	0.001	0.002	0.054	0.000	0.048	0.050	0.002	0.034	0.041

TABLE III
EDIT-DISTANCE RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	10.426	10.426	10.442	13.760	10.576	14.872	16.274	10.426	14.456	10.179	4.679	12.648	11.234	10.442
BGL	5.014	4.930	6.882	8.373	12.524	12.582	12.955	18.598	11.921	10.969	2.981	8.630	9.841	7.900
HDFS	8.820	8.820	16.208	10.762	30.819	17.940	28.340	16.524	18.989	19.843	2.867	10.114	13.641	9.274
HealthApp	19.093	18.502	11.882	16.540	20.277	28.422	16.844	19.598	17.088	21.859	11.595	24.430	13.840	8.540
HPC	1.405	2.015	2.323	2.906	3.182	7.649	3.580	3.218	4.419	4.845	1.275	7.854	2.625	5.129
Mac	19.534	19.882	20.928	19.984	41.804	26.260	21.328	17.048	28.043	28.273	21.417	19.810	34.560	22.593
OpenStack	17.142	28.386	23.330	18.535	28.138	29.173	31.486	23.980	21.881	67.894	5.605	18.582	20.986	27.984
Spark	3.861	3.532	5.246	10.945	9.178	18.116	17.082	16.004	12.968	14.146	2.921	7.910	6.028	6.129
Windows	11.975	6.172	15.758	20.662	10.238	11.834	6.967	6.919	7.667	11.943	6.067	5.624	7.006	4.406
Combined Dataset	13.612	17.302	14.094	18.559	24.144	27.633	21.306	15.858	24.756	19.021	8.721	21.791	22.274	17.454
Industry Dataset	21.959	27.201	24.122	32.280	41.960	68.551	47.006	23.506	37.911	49.145	23.239	31.908	46.690	24.664

Consequently, to get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (1 through 5):

Step 1: Pull the docker image

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py2
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py2 bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python2
```

Step 4: Setup environment

```
$ sh setup_python2.sh
```

Step 5: Run experiment (runs method 10 times)

```
$ sh run_experiment_python2.sh -m AEL -d Apache
# (about 3m)
# (Expect a result of 0.694 log template accuracy and 10.426 edit-distance)
# resulting files can be found at ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python2/logparser/results
```

`-m` specifies the log parsing method to be used and `-d` the dataset.

To reproduce other results, for example, `Drain` on the `BGL` dataset (second cell on the second line of Table II and III), simply replace the method and dataset to be used, namely:

```
$ sh run_experiment_python2.sh -m Drain -d BGL
# (about 5m)
# (Expect a result of 0.341 log template accuracy and 4.930 edit-distance)
# resulting files can be found at ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python2/logparser/results
```

Similarly, all other cells for Methods 1-12 follow a similar workflow.

Method 13 (Python 3 log parsing method)

TABLE II
LOG TEMPLATE ACCURACY RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.000	0.688	0.000	0.000	0.694	0.000	0.270	0.560	0.000	0.424	0.694
BGL	0.341	0.341	0.292	0.082	0.230	0.057	0.067	0.220	0.081	0.324	0.853	0.064	0.207	0.196
HDFS	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.000	0.000
HealthApp	0.164	0.238	0.158	0.136	0.149	0.133	0.138	0.220	0.126	0.166	0.341	0.041	0.322	0.152
HPC	0.644	0.620	0.638	0.632	0.609	0.360	0.632	0.632	0.509	0.632	0.827	0.226	0.661	0.530
Mac	0.172	0.224	0.041	0.132	0.101	0.172	0.162	0.228	0.118	0.042	0.274	0.163	0.148	0.032
OpenStack	0.018	0.018	0.000	0.018	0.008	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000	0.359	0.018	0.119	0.000
Spark	0.194	0.194	0.192	0.004	0.190	0.001	0.006	0.038	0.000	0.208	0.204	0.004	0.543	0.192
Windows	0.154	0.159	0.001	0.154	0.142	0.148	0.153	0.156	0.150	0.006	0.387	0.151	0.140	0.004
Combined Dataset	0.267	0.258	0.214	0.140	0.180	0.140	0.128	0.258	0.092	0.180	0.323	0.067	0.280	0.186
Industry Dataset	0.054	0.056	0.041	0.001	0.022	0.001	0.002	0.054	0.000	0.048	0.050	0.002	0.034	0.041

TABLE III
EDIT-DISTANCE RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	10.426	10.426	10.442	13.760	10.576	14.872	16.274	10.426	14.456	10.179	4.679	12.648	11.234	10.442
BGL	5.014	4.930	6.882	8.373	12.524	12.582	12.955	18.598	11.921	10.969	2.981	8.630	9.841	7.900
HDFS	8.820	8.820	16.208	10.762	30.819	17.940	28.340	16.524	18.989	19.843	2.867	10.114	13.641	9.274
HealthApp	19.093	18.502	11.882	16.540	20.277	28.422	16.844	19.598	17.088	21.859	11.595	24.430	13.840	8.540
HPC	1.405	2.015	2.323	2.906	3.182	7.649	3.580	3.218	4.419	4.845	1.275	7.854	2.625	5.129
Mac	19.534	19.882	20.928	19.984	41.804	26.260	21.328	17.048	28.043	28.273	21.417	19.810	34.560	22.593
OpenStack	17.142	28.386	23.330	18.535	28.138	29.173	31.486	23.980	21.881	67.894	5.605	18.582	20.986	27.984
Spark	3.861	3.532	5.246	10.945	9.178	18.116	17.082	16.004	12.968	14.146	2.921	7.910	6.028	6.129
Windows	11.975	6.172	15.758	20.662	10.238	11.834	6.967	6.919	7.667	11.943	6.067	5.624	7.006	4.406
Combined Dataset	13.612	17.302	14.094	18.559	24.144	27.633	21.306	15.858	24.756	19.021	8.721	21.791	22.274	17.454
Industry Dataset	21.959	27.201	24.122	32.280	41.960	68.551	47.006	23.506	37.911	49.145	23.239	31.908	46.690	24.664

To get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (Step 1 through 5):

Step 1: Pull the docker image

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py3
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py3 bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python3
```

Step 4: Setup environment

```
sh setup_python3.sh
```

Step 5: Run experiment (runs method 10 times)

```
sh run_experiment_python3.sh -m MoLFI -d Apache
# (about 6m)
# (Expect a result of 0.27 log template accuracy and 10.179 edit-distance)
# resulting files can be found at ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python3/logparser/results
```

`-m` specifies the log parsing method to be used and `-d` the dataset.

TABLE II
LOG TEMPLATE ACCURACY RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.000	0.688	0.000	0.000	0.694	0.000	0.270	0.560	0.000	0.424	0.694
BGL	0.341	0.341	0.292	0.082	0.230	0.057	0.067	0.220	0.081	0.324	0.853	0.064	0.207	0.196
HDFS	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.000	0.000
HealthApp	0.164	0.238	0.158	0.136	0.149	0.133	0.138	0.220	0.126	0.166	0.341	0.041	0.322	0.152
HPC	0.644	0.620	0.638	0.632	0.609	0.360	0.632	0.632	0.509	0.632	0.827	0.226	0.661	0.530
Mac	0.172	0.224	0.041	0.132	0.101	0.172	0.162	0.228	0.118	0.042	0.274	0.163	0.148	0.032
OpenStack	0.018	0.018	0.000	0.018	0.008	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000	0.359	0.018	0.119	0.000
Spark	0.194	0.194	0.192	0.004	0.190	0.001	0.006	0.038	0.000	0.208	0.204	0.004	0.543	0.192
Windows	0.154	0.159	0.001	0.154	0.142	0.148	0.153	0.156	0.150	0.006	0.387	0.151	0.140	0.004
Combined Dataset	0.267	0.258	0.214	0.140	0.180	0.140	0.128	0.258	0.092	0.180	0.323	0.067	0.280	0.186
Industry Dataset	0.054	0.056	0.041	0.001	0.022	0.001	0.002	0.054	0.000	0.048	0.050	0.002	0.034	0.041

TABLE III
EDIT-DISTANCE RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLFI	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	10.426	10.426	10.442	13.760	10.576	14.872	16.274	10.426	14.456	10.179	4.679	12.648	11.234	10.442
BGL	5.014	4.930	6.882	8.373	12.524	12.582	12.955	18.598	11.921	10.969	2.981	8.630	9.841	7.900
HDFS	8.820	8.820	16.208	10.762	30.819	17.940	28.340	16.524	18.989	19.843	2.867	10.114	13.641	9.274
HealthApp	19.093	18.502	11.882	16.540	20.277	28.422	16.844	19.598	17.088	21.859	11.595	24.430	13.840	8.540
HPC	1.405	2.015	2.323	2.906	3.182	7.649	3.580	3.218	4.419	4.845	1.275	7.854	2.625	5.129
Mac	19.534	19.882	20.928	19.984	41.804	26.260	21.328	17.048	28.043	28.273	21.417	19.810	34.560	22.593
OpenStack	17.142	28.386	23.330	18.535	28.138	29.173	31.486	23.980	21.881	67.894	5.605	18.582	20.986	27.984
Spark	3.861	3.532	5.246	10.945	9.178	18.116	17.082	16.004	12.968	14.146	2.921	7.910	6.028	6.129
Windows	11.975	6.172	15.758	20.662	10.238	11.834	6.967	6.919	7.667	11.943	6.067	5.624	7.006	4.406
Combined Dataset	13.612	17.302	14.094	18.559	24.144	27.633	21.306	15.858	24.756	19.021	8.721	21.791	22.274	17.454
Industry Dataset	21.959	27.201	24.122	32.280	41.960	68.551	47.006	23.506	37.911	49.145	23.239	31.908	46.690	24.664

Method 14 (Python 3 log parsing method, CUDA GPU access required)

This experiment requires access to GPU, as the respective method (NuLog) involves neural network training. However, not having access to that does not pose a threat to validity, and it is only a small part of the experiments (one column in Table II and III). Our experiments were run on a dual socket AMD Epyc2 machine with 64 cores in total, with a dual Nvidia RTX 2080Ti graphics card setup. Experiments in this section have to be run directly from the source. If you are unable to configure your environment, more information on how to setup this experiment can be found [here](#).

TABLE II
LOG TEMPLATE ACCURACY RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLF	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.000	0.688	0.000	0.000	0.694	0.000	0.270	0.560	0.000	0.424	0.694
BGL	0.341	0.341	0.292	0.082	0.230	0.057	0.067	0.220	0.081	0.324	0.853	0.064	0.207	0.196
HDFS	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.000	0.000
HealthApp	0.164	0.238	0.158	0.136	0.149	0.133	0.138	0.220	0.126	0.166	0.341	0.041	0.322	0.152
HPC	0.644	0.620	0.638	0.632	0.609	0.360	0.632	0.632	0.509	0.632	0.827	0.226	0.661	0.530
Mac	0.172	0.224	0.041	0.132	0.101	0.172	0.162	0.228	0.118	0.042	0.274	0.163	0.148	0.032
OpenStack	0.018	0.018	0.000	0.018	0.008	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000	0.359	0.018	0.119	0.000
Spark	0.194	0.194	0.192	0.004	0.190	0.001	0.006	0.038	0.000	0.208	0.204	0.004	0.543	0.192
Windows	0.154	0.159	0.001	0.154	0.142	0.148	0.153	0.156	0.150	0.006	0.387	0.151	0.140	0.004
Combined Dataset	0.267	0.258	0.214	0.140	0.180	0.140	0.128	0.258	0.092	0.180	0.323	0.067	0.280	0.186
Industry Dataset	0.054	0.056	0.041	0.001	0.022	0.001	0.002	0.054	0.000	0.048	0.050	0.002	0.034	0.041

TABLE III
EDIT-DISTANCE RESULTS AFTER RUNNING EACH METHOD 10 TIMES, FOR EACH DATASET (2K LOGS). THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. WE DEPICT IN BOLD FONT THE BEST RESULTS IN EACH CATEGORY.

Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LenMa	LFA	LKE	LogCluster	LogMine	LogSig	MoLF	NuLog	SHISO	SLCT	Spell
Apache	10.426	10.426	10.442	13.760	10.576	14.872	16.274	10.426	14.456	10.179	4.679	12.648	11.234	10.442
BGL	5.014	4.930	6.882	8.373	12.524	12.582	12.955	18.598	11.921	10.969	2.981	8.630	9.841	7.900
HDFS	8.820	8.820	16.208	10.762	30.819	17.940	28.340	16.524	18.989	19.843	2.867	10.114	13.641	9.274
HealthApp	19.093	18.502	11.882	16.540	20.277	28.422	16.844	19.598	17.088	21.859	11.595	24.430	13.840	8.540
HPC	1.405	2.015	2.323	2.906	3.182	7.649	3.580	3.218	4.419	4.845	1.275	7.854	2.625	5.129
Mac	19.534	19.882	20.928	19.984	41.804	26.260	21.328	17.048	28.043	28.273	21.417	19.810	34.560	22.593
OpenStack	17.142	28.386	23.330	18.535	28.138	29.173	31.486	23.980	21.881	67.894	5.605	18.582	20.986	27.984
Spark	3.861	3.532	5.246	10.945	9.178	18.116	17.082	16.004	12.968	14.146	2.921	7.910	6.028	6.129
Windows	11.975	6.172	15.758	20.662	10.238	11.834	6.967	6.919	7.667	11.943	6.067	5.624	7.006	4.406
Combined Dataset	13.612	17.302	14.094	18.559	24.144	27.633	21.306	15.858	24.756	19.021	8.721	21.791	22.274	17.454
Industry Dataset	21.959	27.201	24.122	32.280	41.960	68.551	47.006	23.506	37.911	49.145	23.239	31.908	46.690	24.664

To get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (Step 1 through 5):

Step 1: Pull the docker image

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py3
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py3 bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/log_parsing_evaluation/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python3
```

Step 4: Setup environment

```
$ pip install natsort scipy==1.3.1 numpy==1.17.4 torchvision==0.4.2 nltk==3.4.5 torch==1.3.1 pandas==0.25.3 Keras==2.3.1 deap==1.3.1 tqdm==4.39.0 recommonmark==0.6.0 scikit_learn==0.22.2.post1 protobuf==3.19.6
```

Step 5: Run experiment (runs method 10 times)

```
$ sh run_experiment_python3.sh -m NuLog -d Apache
# (about 10m)
# (Expect a result of 0.560 log template accuracy and 4.679 edit-distance)
```

If you are not unable to setup the experiment in Docker, follow the steps below (running the code from the source on your machine, outside of Docker, given that you have access to a CUDA GPU).

```
$ git clone https://github.com/spetrescu/gpu-experiment-issre-23.git
$ cd gpu-experiment-issre-23/experiments/log_parsing_experiments/python3
$ python3 -m venv nulog_venv # assuming you have Python 3 installed on your machine
$ source nulog_venv/bin/activate
$ sh setup_python3.sh # make sure all dependencies have been installed (see below)
$ sh run_experiment_python3.sh -m NuLog -d Apache
# (about 10m)
# (Expect a result of 0.560 log template accuracy and 4.679 edit-distance)
```

Make sure all following dependencies are installed before running NuLog (you can check by using `pip list` in the virtual env)

```
# scipy==1.3.1
# numpy==1.17.4
# torchvision==0.4.2
# nltk==3.4.5
# torch==1.3.1
# pandas==0.25.3
# Keras==2.3.1
```

```
# deap==1.3.1
# tqdm==4.39.0
# recommonmark==0.6.0
# scikit_learn==0.22.2.post1
```

(4.2) Heterogeneity analysis (Figure 4, Table IV)

We analyze a variety of datasets, and assess their heterogeneity by considering three metrics, namely *unique number of words*, *unique number of characters*, and *unique number of log lengths*.

To reproduce Figure 4 (based on the measurements from Table IV), follow the steps below (1-5):

Step 1: *Pull the docker image*

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py3
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: *Start the image and bash shell*

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:py3 bash
```

Step 3: *Go to path for current experiment*

```
$ cd ~/analysis-data-heterogeneity
```

Step 4: *Generate figures*

```
$ sh measure_statistics.sh
# (about 1m)
# (generates three figures, which correspond to the three subfigures below)
```


Fig. 4. (a) Unique number of characters versus unique of words. (b) Unique number of log lines' character length versus unique number of words. (c) Unique number of log lines' character length versus unique number of characters.

Step 5 (optional): Visualize figure(s)

To visualize a subfigure (for example, subfigure (a) above), run the command below.

```
$ docker cp <container_id>:/root/analysis-data-heterogeneity/entity_a.pdf <path_on_host>
# (run the above command from host, outside of the Docker container)
```

To discover the `container_id`, run `docker ps -a` on the host machine, outside of the Docker container. Lastly, replace `<path_on_host>` with the path where you would like to save the visualisations.

```
# Example (from host)
$ docker cp e461dc9cc42c:~/analysis-data-heterogeneity/entity_a.pdf ./
```

(4.3) Proxy metrics weighing (Table V)

To reproduce this table we (1) computed the normalized values for the proxy metrics (by dividing all measurements by the highest element on each respective row) and (2) subsequently computed the variance. We display below the entire process of obtaining the values showcased in the paper (Table V).

Below, we display:

- Initial table (Table IV)
- Normalized table
- Final values table (Table V)

Initial table (Table V)

Dataset	Apache	BGL	HDFS	HealthApp	HPC	Mac
No. unique words	874	2068	3599	1512	510	2981
No. unique characters	46	75	56	71	65	90
No. unique log lengths	9	114	59	55	50	186

Dataset	OpenStack	Spark	Windows	Combined	Industry
No. unique words	1445	1970	1206	3123	4421
No. unique characters	72	70	82	91	92
No. unique log lengths	50	63	66	157	181

Normalized table (Table V)

Dataset	Apache	BGL	HDFS	HealthApp	HPC	Mac
No. unique words	0.197	0.467	0.814	0.342	0.115	0.674
No. unique characters	0.5	0.815	0.608	0.771	0.706	0.978
No. unique log lengths	0.049	0.629	0.325	0.303	0.276	0.027

Dataset	OpenStack	Spark	Windows	Combined	Industry
No. unique words	0.326	0.445	0.272	0.706	1
No. unique characters	0.782	0.760	0.891	0.989	1
No. unique log lengths	0.276	0.348	0.364	0.867	1

Final values table (Table V)

No.	Metric	Σ^2
1	No. unique words	0.278
2	No. unique characters	0.159
3	No. unique log lengths	0.331

(4.4) Mixing (Table VI)

In this section, we showcase how to reproduce Table VI, by showcasing how to reproduce the results for a particular dataset and method, namely for `Apache` and `AEL`. Specifically, we reproduce the following section of Table VI.

TABLE VI

PERFORMANCE AFTER INCREASING HETEROGENEITY VIA MIXING. ALL DATASETS CONTAIN 2K LOGS. THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. THE SCORE IN PARENTHESIS REPRESENTS THE AMOUNT OF LOGS THAT WERE REPLACED THROUGH MIXING OTHER DATA, E.G., APACHE (5) HAS HAD 5% OF ITS MOST FREQUENT LOG LINES REPLACED BY HETEROGENEOUS LOGS FROM OTHER DATASETS.

<i>H</i> level	Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM
0.219	Apache init	0.694/10.426	0.694/10.426	0.694/10.442
0.530	Apache (5)	0.653/15.925	0.653/15.923	0.653/15.369
0.640	Apache (10)	0.618/19.596	0.618/19.602	0.618/19.414
0.737	Apache (15)	0.586/23.468	0.586/23.495	0.586/22.809
0.816	Apache (20)	0.552/27.504	0.552/27.547	0.552/26.877
0.886	Apache (25)	0.514/32.265	0.514/32.135	0.514/31.34
0.259	HPC init	0.644/1.405	0.620/2.015	0.638/2.323
0.524	HPC (5)	0.605/6.510	0.581/7.081	0.599/7.257
0.661	HPC (10)	0.566/11.734	0.542/12.272	0.560/12.301
0.735	HPC (15)	0.525/16.720	0.501/17.300	0.519/17.124
0.817	HPC (20)	0.486/22.040	0.462/22.566	0.480/21.809
0.881	HPC (25)	0.447/27.875	0.423/28.234	0.441/27.349
0.608	BGL init	0.341/5.014	0.341/4.930	0.292/6.882
0.756	BGL (5)	0.321/11.004	0.321/10.940	0.273/12.665
0.833	BGL (10)	0.303/15.623	0.303/15.495	0.254/16.325
0.908	BGL (15)	0.285/20.665	0.285/20.639	0.251/20.970
0.949	BGL (20)	0.265/25.665	0.265/25.771	0.216/25.926
0.868	Mac init	0.172/19.534	0.224/19.882	0.041/20.928
0.901	Mac (5)	0.169/25.184	0.217/25.518	0.041/26.410
0.919	Mac (8)	0.169/28.507	0.217/28.838	0.041/29.730
0.830	Combined Dataset	0.267/13.612	0.258/17.302	0.214/14.094
1	Industry Dataset	0.054/21.959	0.056/27.201	0.041/24.122

To get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (Step 1 through 4):

Step 1: *Pull the docker image*

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:mixing
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:mixing bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/mixing
```

Step 4: Run experiment

```
$ sh experiment_mixing_vi.sh -d "Apache" -m "AEL" -x
# (about 5m)
```

`-d` specifies the dataset, `-m` the method, and `-x` if mixing is to be applied.

```
# Usage: ./experiment_mixing_vi.sh [-d dataset] [-m method] [-x]
# Options:
# -d: Dataset (dataset to be used)
# -m: Method (log parsing method to test)
# -x: Mixing (true if flagged)
```

For this experiment, fuzzing is not to be applied. At the end of running the commands above you should be able to reproduce the section corresponding to `Apache` and `AEL`. Similarly, for the other sections of the table, the arguments of the script need to be changed accordingly. For example, for reproducing the results for `Drain` on the `Apache` dataset, the following command needs to be run:

```
$ sh experiment_mixing_table_vi.sh -d "Apache" -m "Drain" -x
```

(4.5) Mixing and fuzzing (Table VII)

Similarly to the workflow for reproducing Table VI, reproducing Table VII requires following the steps below. Specifically, we showcase how to reproduce the following section of Table VII (all other sections of the table follow a similar workflow).

TABLE VII
PERFORMANCE ON APACHE, HPC, BGL, AND MAC AFTER INCREASING HETEROGENEITY VIA MIXING AND FUZZING. MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS, ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. THE SCORE IN PARENTHESIS REPRESENTS THE AMOUNT OF LOGS THAT WERE REPLACED VIA MIXING, E.G., APACHE (25) HAS HAD 25% OF ITS MOST FREQUENT LOG LINES REPLACED BY HETEROGENEOUS LOGS FROM OTHER DATASETS.

<i>H</i> level	Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LFA	LogMine
0.219	Apache init	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.688/10.576	0.694/10.426
0.886	Apache (25)	0.514/32.265	0.514/32.135	0.514/31.34	0.509/20.243	0.515/32.016
1	Apache (25) fuzzed	0.078/77.541	0.118/76.820	0.059/45.555	0.231/38.866	0.060/82.104
0.259	HPC init	0.644/1.405	0.620/2.015	0.638/2.323	0.609/3.182	0.632/3.218
0.881	HPC (25)	0.447/27.875	0.423/28.234	0.441/27.349	0.296/17.434	0.436/30.290
0.954	HPC (25) fuzzed	0.242/97.492	0.260/93.240	0.219/45.718	0.141/42.085	0.236/100.324
0.608	BGL init	0.341/5.014	0.341/4.930	0.292/6.882	0.230/12.524	0.220/18.598
0.949	BGL (20)	0.265/25.665	0.265/25.771	0.216/25.926	0.150/22.355	0.104/33.728
1	BGL (20) fuzzed	0.143/95.117	0.143/96.156	0.073/62.862	0.077/46.389	0.016/79.8035
0.868	Mac init	0.172/19.534	0.224/19.882	0.041/20.928	0.101/41.804	0.228/17.048
0.919	Mac (8)	0.169/28.508	0.217/28.838	0.041/29.73	0.098/51.167	0.224/25.933
1	Mac (8) fuzzed	0.018/135.994	0.011/116.706	0.001/112.063	0.013/79.454	0.022/207.376
0.830	Combined Dataset	0.267/13.612	0.258/17.302	0.214/14.094	0.180/24.144	0.258/15.858
1	Industry Dataset	0.054/21.959	0.056/27.201	0.041/24.122	0.022/41.960	0.054/23.506

To get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (Step 1 through 4):

Step 1: Pull the docker image

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:mixing
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:mixing bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/mixing_and_fuzzing
```

Step 4: Run experiment

```
$ sh experiment_fuzzing_vii.sh -d "Apache" -m "AEL" -x -f
```

`-d` specifies the dataset, `-m` the method, `-x` if mixing is to be applied, and `-f` if fuzzing is to be applied.

```
# Usage: ./experiment_fuzzing_vii.sh [-d dataset] [-m method] [-x] [-f]
# Options:
# -d: Dataset (dataset to be used)
# -m: Method (log parsing method to test)
# -x: Mixing (true if flagged)
# -f: Fuzzing (true if flagged)
```

At the end of running the commands above you should be able to reproduce the section corresponding to `Apache` and `AEL`. Similarly, for reproducing the other sections of the table, the arguments of the script need to be changed accordingly. For example, for reproducing the results for `Drain` on the `Apache` dataset, the following command needs to be run:

```
$ sh experiment_fuzzing_vii.sh -d "Apache" -m "Drain" -x -f
```

(4.6) Unlabeled comparison (Table VIII)

In this section we provide instructions on how to reproduce Table VIII. Specifically, we showcase how to reproduce the following row of Table VIII (all other rows follow a similar workflow):

TABLE VIII
COMPARISON BETWEEN H LEVEL OBTAINED LEVERAGING LABELED DATA VERSUS FULLY AUTOMATICALLY BASED ON PARSING RESULTS AND WITHOUT REQUIRING ACCESS TO LABELS.

Dataset	H level gdt	H level parsed
Apache parsed (25) fuzzed	1	0.960
HPC parsed (25) fuzzed	0.954	0.938
BGL parsed (20) fuzzed	1	1
Mac parsed (8) fuzzed	1	0.906

To get you started, please follow the steps displayed below (Step 1 through 4):

Step 1: *Pull the docker image*

```
$ docker pull spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:mixing
# (about 5min)
```

Step 2: Start the image and bash shell

```
$ docker run -it spetrescu/log-parsing-evaluator:mixing bash
```

Step 3: Go to path for current experiment

```
$ cd ~/automated_mixing_and_fuzzing
```

Step 4: Run experiment

```
$ sh experiment_automated_mixing_and_fuzzing_viii.sh -d "Apache"
```

-d specifies the dataset to be used

```
# Usage: ./experiment_automated_mixing_and_fuzzing_viii.sh [-d dataset]
# Options:
#   -d: Dataset (either Apache or HPC or BGL or Mac)
```

At the end of running the commands above you should be able to reproduce the section corresponding to `Apache`. Similarly, for reproducing the other rows of the table, the arguments of the script need to be changed accordingly. For example, for reproducing the results for `HPC`, the following command needs to be run:

```
$ sh experiment_automated_mixing_and_fuzzing_viii.sh -d "HPC"
```

Should you encounter any issues, additional support and examples on reproducing the experiments can be found [here](#).

Citation

```
@INPROCEEDINGS{petrescu2023issre,  
author={Petrescu, Stefan and den Hengst, Floris and Uta, Alexandru and Rellermeier, Jan  
S.},  
booktitle={34th IEEE International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE)},  
title={Log Parsing Evaluation in the Era of Modern Software Systems},  
year={2023}}
```

Appendix - example usage **logchimera**

Development MacOS

1. Install **miniconda**

```
$ mkdir -p ~/miniconda3  
$ curl <https://repo.anaconda.com/miniconda/Miniconda3-latest-MacOSX-arm64.sh> -o ~/minico  
nda3/miniconda.sh  
$ bash ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh -b -u -p ~/miniconda3  
$ rm -rf ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh
```

2. Initialize `miniconda` for bash / zsh shells

```
$ ~/miniconda3/bin/conda init bash
$ ~/miniconda3/bin/conda init zsh
```

3. Create `logchimera` virtual environment and activate it

```
$ conda create --name logchimera python=3.9 -y
$ conda activate logchimera
$ pip install poetry
```

4. Install package

```
$ git clone <https://github.com/spetrescu/logchimera.git>
$ cd logchimera
$ git checkout issre_23_code
$ poetry install
```

5. Check if installation was successful

```
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import function_test
>>> # go to Example usage ISSRE 23 below
```

If the installation was successful, please refer below to section `Example usage ISSRE 23`.

Development Linux

1. Install `miniconda`

```
$ mkdir -p ~/miniconda3
$ wget <https://repo.anaconda.com/miniconda/Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh> -O ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh
$ bash ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh -b -u -p ~/miniconda3
$ rm -rf ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh
```

1. Initialize `miniconda` for bash / zsh shells

```
$ ~/miniconda3/bin/conda init bash
$ ~/miniconda3/bin/conda init zsh
```

1. Create `logchimera` virtual environment and activate it

```
$ conda create --name logchimera python=3.9 -y
$ conda activate logchimera
$ pip install poetry
```

1. Install package

```
$ git clone <https://github.com/spetrescu/logchimera.git>
$ cd logchimera
$ git checkout issre_23_code
$ poetry install
```

1. Check if installation was successful

```
$ python
Python 3.9.17 (main, Jul 5 2023, 20:41:20)
[GCC 11.2.0] :: Anaconda, Inc. on linux
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import estimate_heterogeneity
>>>
```

If the installation was successful, please refer below to section `Example usage ISSRE 23`.

Example usage ISSRE 23

Use `logchimera` for mixing

TABLE VI

PERFORMANCE AFTER INCREASING HETEROGENEITY VIA MIXING. ALL DATASETS CONTAIN 2K LOGS. THE MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS AND ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. THE SCORE IN PARENTHESIS REPRESENTS THE AMOUNT OF LOGS THAT WERE REPLACED THROUGH MIXING OTHER DATA, E.G., APACHE (5) HAS HAD 5% OF ITS MOST FREQUENT LOG LINES REPLACED BY HETEROGENEOUS LOGS FROM OTHER DATASETS.

<i>H</i> level	Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM
0.219	Apache init	0.694/10.426	0.694/10.426	0.694/10.442
0.530	Apache (5)	0.653/15.925	0.653/15.923	0.653/15.369
0.640	Apache (10)	0.618/19.596	0.618/19.602	0.618/19.414
0.737	Apache (15)	0.586/23.468	0.586/23.495	0.586/22.809
0.816	Apache (20)	0.552/27.504	0.552/27.547	0.552/26.877
0.886	Apache (25)	0.514/32.265	0.514/32.135	0.514/31.34
0.259	HPC init	0.644/1.405	0.620/2.015	0.638/2.323
0.524	HPC (5)	0.605/6.510	0.581/7.081	0.599/7.257
0.661	HPC (10)	0.566/11.734	0.542/12.272	0.560/12.301
0.735	HPC (15)	0.525/16.720	0.501/17.300	0.519/17.124
0.817	HPC (20)	0.486/22.040	0.462/22.566	0.480/21.809
0.881	HPC (25)	0.447/27.875	0.423/28.234	0.441/27.349
0.608	BGL init	0.341/5.014	0.341/4.930	0.292/6.882
0.756	BGL (5)	0.321/11.004	0.321/10.940	0.273/12.665
0.833	BGL (10)	0.303/15.623	0.303/15.495	0.254/16.325
0.908	BGL (15)	0.285/20.665	0.285/20.639	0.251/20.970
0.949	BGL (20)	0.265/25.665	0.265/25.771	0.216/25.926
0.868	Mac init	0.172/19.534	0.224/19.882	0.041/20.928
0.901	Mac (5)	0.169/25.184	0.217/25.518	0.041/26.410
0.919	Mac (8)	0.169/28.507	0.217/28.838	0.041/29.730
0.830	Combined Dataset	0.267/13.612	0.258/17.302	0.214/14.094
1	Industry Dataset	0.054/21.959	0.056/27.201	0.041/24.122

```

# Apache example. To obtain different levels of heterogeneity, vary the heterogeneity level
l (the second parameter) from 0 to 1. Example values: 0.22 (for Apache 5)
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/Apache/Apache_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.2
2, "Apache")
Heterogeneity is: 0.5304069912609239 for dataset datasets_mixing/5_Apache.csv # correspond
s to the second row in table vi (0.530, Apache 5)
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/Apache/Apache_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.4
0, "Apache")
Heterogeneity is: 0.6399750312109863 for dataset datasets_mixing/10_Apache.csv # correspon
ds to the third row in table vi (0.640, Apache 10)
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/Apache/Apache_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.5
7, "Apache")
Heterogeneity is: 0.7366891385767791 for dataset datasets_mixing/15_Apache.csv # correspon
ds to the fourth row in table vi (0.737, Apache 15)
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/Apache/Apache_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.9
5, "Apache")
Heterogeneity is: 0.8861722846441948 for dataset datasets_mixing/25_Apache.csv # correspon
ds to 0.886, Apache 25

```

```

# BGL example. To obtain different levels of heterogeneity, vary the heterogeneity level
(the second parameter) from 0 to 1. Example values: 0.69 (for BGL 15)
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/BGL/BGL_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.25, "BG
L")
Heterogeneity is: 0.7564544319600499 for dataset datasets_mixing/5_BGL.csv # corresponds t
o 0.756, BGL 5
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/BGL/BGL_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.47, "BG
L")
Heterogeneity is: 0.8325243445692885 for dataset datasets_mixing/10_BGL.csv # corresponds
to 0.833, BGL 10
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/BGL/BGL_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.69, "BG
L")
Heterogeneity is: 0.9082347066167291 for dataset datasets_mixing/15_BGL.csv # corresponds
to 0.908, BGL 15
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/BGL/BGL_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.93, "BG
L")
Heterogeneity is: 0.9489438202247192 for dataset datasets_mixing/20_BGL.csv # corresponds
to 0.949, BGL 20

```

```

# HPC example
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/HPC/HPC_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.60, "HPC")
Heterogeneity is: 0.7347465667915107 for dataset datasets_mixing/15_HPC.csv # corresponds to 0.730, HPC 15

```

```

# Mac example
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/Mac/Mac_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.40, "Mac")
Heterogeneity is: 0.9011235955056179 for dataset datasets_mixing/5_Mac.csv # corresponds to 0.901, Mac 5

```

Use **logchimera** for fuzzing

TABLE VII

PERFORMANCE ON APACHE, HPC, BGL, AND MAC AFTER INCREASING HETEROGENEITY VIA MIXING AND FUZZING. MEASUREMENTS ARE AVERAGED OVER 10 RUNS, ALL STANDARD DEVIATIONS WERE BELOW 1%. THE SCORE IN PARENTHESIS REPRESENTS THE AMOUNT OF LOGS THAT WERE REPLACED VIA MIXING, E.G., APACHE (25) HAS HAD 25% OF ITS MOST FREQUENT LOG LINES REPLACED BY HETEROGENEOUS LOGS FROM OTHER DATASETS.

<i>H</i> level	Dataset	AEL	Drain	IPLoM	LFA	LogMine
0.219	Apache init	0.694	0.694	0.694	0.688/10.576	0.694/10.426
0.886	Apache (25)	0.514/32.265	0.514/32.135	0.514/31.34	0.509/20.243	0.515/32.016
1	Apache (25) fuzzed	0.078/77.541	0.118/76.820	0.059/45.555	0.231/38.866	0.060/82.104
0.259	HPC init	0.644/1.405	0.620/2.015	0.638/2.323	0.609/3.182	0.632/3.218
0.881	HPC (25)	0.447/27.875	0.423/28.234	0.441/27.349	0.296/17.434	0.436/30.290
0.954	HPC (25) fuzzed	0.242/97.492	0.260/93.240	0.219/45.718	0.141/42.085	0.236/100.324
0.608	BGL init	0.341/5.014	0.341/4.930	0.292/6.882	0.230/12.524	0.220/18.598
0.949	BGL (20)	0.265/25.665	0.265/25.771	0.216/25.926	0.150/22.355	0.104/33.728
1	BGL (20) fuzzed	0.143/95.117	0.143/96.156	0.073/62.862	0.077/46.389	0.016/79.8035
0.868	Mac init	0.172/19.534	0.224/19.882	0.041/20.928	0.101/41.804	0.228/17.048
0.919	Mac (8)	0.169/28.508	0.217/28.838	0.041/29.73	0.098/51.167	0.224/25.933
1	Mac (8) fuzzed	0.018/135.994	0.011/116.706	0.001/112.063	0.013/79.454	0.022/207.376
0.830	Combined Dataset	0.267/13.612	0.258/17.302	0.214/14.094	0.180/24.144	0.258/15.858
1	Industry Dataset	0.054/21.959	0.056/27.201	0.041/24.122	0.022/41.960	0.054/23.506

```

# Apache example
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)

```

```
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import fuzz_data, increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/Apache/Apache_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.95, "Apache")
Heterogeneity is: 0.8861722846441948 for dataset datasets_mixing/25_Apache.csv # corresponds to 0.886, Apache 25
>>> fuzz_data("datasets_mixing/25_Apache.csv", "Apache", 25)
Heterogeneity is: 1.0 for dataset fuzzing/Apache_25_fuzzed.csv
```

```
# HPC example
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import fuzz_data, increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/HPC/HPC_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.99, "HPC")
Heterogeneity is: 0.8810786516853932 for dataset datasets_mixing/25_HPC.csv # corresponds to 0.881, BGL HPC 25
>>> fuzz_data("datasets_mixing/25_HPC.csv", "HPC", 25)
Heterogeneity is: 0.9094831460674158 for dataset fuzzing/HPC_25_fuzzed.csv
```

```
# BGL example
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import fuzz_data, increase_heterogeneity_for_file
>>> increase_heterogeneity_for_file("experiments/BGL/BGL_2k.log_structured.csv", 0.93, "BGL")
Heterogeneity is: 0.9489438202247192 for dataset datasets_mixing/20_BGL.csv # corresponds to 0.949, BGL 20
>>> fuzz_data("datasets_mixing/20_BGL.csv", "BGL", 20)
Heterogeneity is: 1.0 for dataset fuzzing/BGL_20_fuzzed.csv
```

```
# Mac example
$ python
Python 3.9.16 (main, Mar  8 2023, 04:29:44)
[Clang 14.0.6 ] :: Anaconda, Inc. on darwin
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> from logchimera.logchimera import fuzz_data
>>> fuzz_data("datasets_mixing/8_Mac.csv", "Mac", 8)
Heterogeneity is: 1.0 for dataset fuzzing/Mac_8_fuzzed.csv
```